

Capacity Building For Lecturers In Nigerian Universities: The Pros And The Cons

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ABSTRACT

This paper examined capacity building for lecturers in Nigerian universities: the pros and cons. Capacity building involves the development of the available skills for better productivity in an organization. Despite the fact that universities in Nigeria have skilled and capable lecturers, there is need to further develop these skill sets for optimal productivity in the universities. This is due to the fact that the society is an ever-changing one and with it, the different sectors of the society such as the educational sector are continuously evolving. Thus, it is necessary for the lecturers to evolve alongside the emerging trends in university education. Moreover, despite the benefits of capacity building of the lecturers in the universities, there are negative aspects to it such as brain drain. The paper discussed the concepts of capacity building, lecturers and the pros and cons associated with capacity building of lecturers and in universities in Nigeria. The paper also highlighted the challenges that serve as hindrances in capacity building for lecturers and in Nigerian universities some of which include lack of funding, lack of training and retraining of lecturers, poor contribution to research, amongst others. The paper concluded that the administrators in universities in Nigeria need to prioritize capacity building of its lecturers to enhance productivity within their universities and to further bring about sustainable university education in Nigeria. The suggestions proposed the following courses of workable action that university administrators and relevant stakeholders could apply to promote capacity building in Nigerian universities.

Keywords: Capacity Building, Lecturers, University Education, Pros and Cons

INTRODUCTION

The society is dynamic and individuals are made with the ability to adapt to such dynamism in order to evolve alongside the society. Individuals as well as institutions and organizations' capacity need to be built and boosted to enhance creativity, high productivity and financial independence (Ajewole, 2014). Thus, Ochai (2012) maintained that inventing external measures that are designed and established to influence behaviour of individuals, groups or organizations in developing capacity is very necessary when expecting a desirable outcome from participants. The output of a student can be influenced by the teacher's capacity. This is in accordance with previous studies by Loyalka, Popova, Li & Shi (2019) on the issue of students' academic performance which found that many variables affect students' academic performances; yet, lecturers capacity development remains one of the most significant drivers of students' academic successes." Capacity building initiatives, therefore, play a crucial role in empowering lecturers, enhancing their skills, and ultimately improving the educational outcomes for students. Muhammad, Abubakar, Audi, & Manya-Manya (2024) opined that because of depressed economy universities are facing challenges, increasing access, recruitment and training of quality academic staff, supply of

adequate teaching aids, construction of adequate learning facilities, poor infrastructure, lack of capacity building, office space for staff, lack of classrooms, libraries, laboratories, workshop room, sanctuary facilities, poor working condition, and lack of training and retraining of staff. is in the light of this background that the aim of this paper is to identify ways in which the university administration can identify the pros and cons of capacity building for lecturers in Nigerian universities. The objective of this study is to examine how capacity building programs affected the professional competence, teaching effectiveness and research productivity of lecturers in Nigeria. The study is important due to the fact that capacity building for lecturers is a necessity for the growth and development of the students who will graduate and contribute to the society. The gap identified in this study is that although capacity building would be beneficial to the lecturers, there is limited examination of the disadvantages of the capacity building of lecturers which may be detrimental to the university.

Capacity Building

Capacity deals with the capabilities of individuals. Similarly, Stevens (2014) ascertained that capacity is the related term of capabilities and competencies of individuals or organizations. Capacity building is thus the development of the abilities and skillsets of individuals in an organization. It is the continuous process of updating knowledge for the effect and efficient performances of certain jobs (Egbula & Ekpo, 2016). Capacity building for lecturers in Nigerian universities is vital for enhancing teaching, research, and community service capabilities. It is the continuous process of developing and strengthening the skills, competencies, and abilities of the lecturers in the university to perform their jobs effectively. In the same vein, Philbin (2016) observed that capacity building is a process of developing and strengthening the talents, instincts, abilities, processes and resources that individuals, organisations and communities got to survive, adapt and thrive within the fast-changing world. Additionally, Ebikeseye and Puyate (2022) mentioned that it is the process of enhancing the knowledge, skills, and capacities of a person, group, organisational sector, or nation in order to bring about sustained and self-sustaining gains in productivity." Capacity building requires continuous improvement in attitude, knowledge and skills of lectures through continuous learning in the dual mode universities (Dada, Zaifada, & Ofie, 2019). The Nigerian National Policy on Education has stressed the need for continuous professional development for academic staff and investment in infrastructure (Federal Ministry of Education, 2013). Capacity building needs of lecturers in universities include: new knowledge and skills to carry out their duties effectively, skills on research and development, ideas needed for knowledge creation and team spirits to deliver lectures appropriately (Madumere-Obike, Ukala & Nwabueze, 2015). Furthermore, Uchendu (2015) submitted that when the capacities of people are built, they can guide their internal development and activities as they would have been skilled and knowledgeable to act in way that would improve their standard of living. Similarly, effective capacity building of the lecturers in Nigerian universities equates to improved educational outcomes, improved research output, and all round development of the lecturer.

University Education

A university is an institution of higher learning where individuals gain academic knowledge and acquire skillsets to enable them contribute to society. Alemu (2018) identified the university as a higher learning institution that brings men and women to a high level of intellectual development in the arts and science, and in the traditional professional disciplines, and promotes high-level research. Ofor-Douglas (2024a) affirmed that it is an institution on which the future of every country depends, as it produces elites for the growth and technological advancement of every country at a given period of time. Naziev (2017) averred that education is the socially organized and regulated process of socially transference of significant experience from the previous generations to the following generations. Education is a very important factor in human development, and it brings about critical thinking, fosters changes in human life in teaching someone how to make important decisions, boost creativity, enhances individuals' potentials and importance to the society, and has been ultimately explained to be a passage for progressive (Charrize, 2023). In the same vein, education is consistently argued to be a very important factor in human capacity

building and achieving capacity development (Nicholl, 2014). Thus, university education is education received from an institution of higher learning that develops an individual's critical thinking and allows for creativity, improving the skillsets of individuals which would benefit the larger society upon graduation. In the university system, the lecturers and other teaching staffs form the core of the knowledge base, as they have the crucial task of teaching and disseminating knowledge to the students who have enrolled to undertake courses in the university (Gayson, 2022). Capacity building is essential for improving teaching and learning outcomes in universities. University education needs capacity building when:

1. There is a need to improve teaching and learning outcomes
2. New technologies are introduced
3. There are changes in curriculum or teaching methods

Franz and Archibald (2018) stated that capacity building may be used in the classroom in four distinct ways: human, organisational, structural, and material." Human potential includes both the cognitive capacity (such as knowledge and abilities) and the volitional ability (such as desire, patience, and tenacity) to bring about the required changes. An organization such as the university's internal capabilities depend heavily on the level of interaction, cooperation, and communication among its employees. This capability is independent of the people employed by the company. What an organisation requires in terms of money, supplies, and tools to carry out its goals and implement change is referred to as its "material capacity." It is well understood that the many approaches to capacity building are interconnected, and that success in one area depends on development in another.

Pros and Cons of Capacity Building for Lecturers in Universities in Nigeria

Capacity building for lecturers despite its advantages is not bereft of a disadvantage. The following serve as the pros and cons of capacity building of lecturers in Nigerian universities:

Pros

1. **Quality Education:** Capacity building for lecturers in Nigerian universities inevitably equates to quality education in the universities. Quality in this sense tends to look at the importance of improving the quality of education with discussions gearing towards accreditation, curriculum implementation and institutional framework which ensures universities deliver high quality education for global competitiveness (Ofor-Douglas,2024a) Education is the foundation for the right footing if a nation intends to grow tall in the affairs of doing things locally and globally for sustainability (Ofor-Douglas, 2024b). A nation without quality education is like a blind man working in the street without guidance, and such a nation, cannot grow to attain sustainability in the country. The quality of university education is greatly dependent on the competencies of educators. Quality education is pivotal for productivity improvement, equipping individuals with skills and knowledge that enhance efficiency, management effectiveness, produce quality, technological advancement, regulatory compliance and employee expertise (Yadav & Marwah, 2015).
2. **Improved Research Output:** Another pro to capacity building for lecturers in Nigerian universities is that of improved research output. Research output refers to academic publications by lecturers in books, journals, articles, conference papers, amongst others. In a similar pattern, Okendo (2018) stated that research output includes work that has been researched upon and published in journals, book chapters, monographs, articles, technical reports, conference papers amongst others. The visibility of a university is highly dependent on its research output. Research is one of the elements of a university that sets them apart from their competitors within the context of ranking and a key indicator used to place institutions on the ivy-league table of world ranking universities (Gunawan, Barasa, & Tua, 2018). Additionally, Salami and Ajayi (2022) noted that universities with strong faculty research output are more likely to attract collaborations, funding, and recognition, contributing to sustained institutional growth and credibility. Akani (2017) asserted that capacity building in Nigerian universities will aid in strengthening the internal institutions to be forward-looking, success-driven, broaden the resource base of the university

by collaborating with other universities and build the capacity of the staff to engage in researches that will attract international attention and grants to the university.

3. **Motivated Lecturers:** Motivation of the lecturers in Nigerian universities is another advantage added to the pro list for capacity building of lectures in Nigerian universities. Motivation in this context involves a form of encouragement on lecturers for the enhancement of productivity in the university. Munyengabe et al. (2017) mentioned that motivation involves a series of modifying and directing human behaviours into desired patterns of work. Increased motivation equates to increased job performance. Agreeing with this assertion, Ofor-Douglas (2019) rightly stated that an organization that has well motivated staff will have increased performance. Additionally, Okafor, Ohamobi, & Manafa, (2021) cited in Ofor-Douglas (2024c) maintained that students that are taught in a conducive environment with motivated lecturers and adequate facilities will always have good academic performance without examination malpractice.

Cons

Brain drain: A very problematic disadvantage of capacity building of lecturers in Nigerian universities is that of brain drain. Brain drain is the massive migration of trained professionals from their home countries to developed countries where their skills can be better appreciated. It is the exodus of skills from one country to the other. Aligning with these notions, Akinola and Adekile (2024) posited that brain drain is the movement of highly skilled individuals from developing nations to other countries, leading to a depletion of talent in their home countries. Similarly, Anokye et al. (2019) stated that in search of better jobs and opportunities, experienced professionals move both within and outside of Africa, resulting to a phenomenon which known as brain drain. Brain drain inevitably causes a decline in the society as the skills needed to develop the nation are being transferred to develop other nations. In a related position, Jacob and Atobauka (2021) acknowledged the fact that many academic personnels in Nigeria's higher education (university education inclusive) institutions are departing due to the unfavourable working conditions and will no doubt leave socio-economic effects on the country if left to linger. Capacity building despite its benefits could lead to brain drain in the sense that the universities train and develop these individuals only for these lecturers to seek greener pastures elsewhere after the university has utilized its resources in training them. This behaviour can be referred to as turnover tendencies of lecturers in which Calvin et al. (2023) averred that it has greatly impacted the institution's costs related to recruiting and selecting new personnel, training of newly recruited employees and loss of knowledge acquired by the staff while on the job.

Problems Facing Capacity Building for Lecturers in Nigerian Universities

A plethora of problems have been found to hinder capacity building for lecturers in Nigerian universities. Arguably, Hagelsteen et al. (2022) opined that some of these problems included but are not limited to poor information communication technology in the universities, lack of research by the lecturers, lack of well-equipped laboratories, poor management of university education, poor research funding in the university and poorly paid university lecturers amongst others. The author has gleaned the following problems as challenges to capacity building for lecturers in Nigerian universities to include:

1. **Lack of Funding:** The major challenge from which other challenges to capacity building for lecturers in Nigerian universities arise is no doubt the lack of funding. Funding in the context of capacity building of lecturers in Nigerian universities involves the use of available financial resource to implement capacity building projects and programmes in the university. Public universities in Nigeria are mainly funded by the federal and state governments. It goes without saying that these universities are grossly underfunded leading to a decline in the capacity building of lecturers in the universities. The successes of Nigerian universities are restricted by poor funding in the context of the accelerating inflation in the country. In other words, Ogunode & Oluseun (2020) posited that inadequate funding of Nigerian higher education institutions is a major problem facing the administration of professional development

programmes for employees (lecturers) across higher education institutions. In a related position, many universities in Nigeria struggle with insufficient financial resource, leading to limited capacity for staff development and infrastructural development. These universities also lack the financial muscles required to organize comprehensive training programs.

2. **Lack of Facilities:** The lack of adequate facilities for capacity building in Nigerian universities has affected capacity building efforts of these universities. What makes university education unique is the level of infrastructural facilities it holds as this helps to portray a high standard of its institution in the eyes of the society (Ofor-Douglas, 2024d). As a result of the poor funding for capacity building of lecturers in Nigerian universities, there is a lack of facilities for capacity building of lecturers. In order for capacity building policies to thrive in the university, up-to date and adequate facilities for training, research and overall development of the lecturer has to be put in place. Moreover, Chikwe et al. (2015) posited that in Nigerian universities, the necessary facilities required for research by lecturers are lacking or grossly inadequate. These facilities include but are not limited to ICT equipment, internet connectivity, up-to-date research materials (textbooks), amongst others. In the same vein, Somadina et al. (2024) rightly observed that workshops, libraries and laboratories are ill-equipped and obsolete facilities for education for education are difficult to replace if not impossible.

3. **Lack of Training and Retraining of Lecturers:** Another challenge facing capacity building of lecturers in Nigerian universities is that of the lack of training and retraining of lecturers. Meanwhile, Patrick (2021) observed that lecturers' professional development in Nigeria is not impressive in terms of availability and accessibility and the ones that are available are disorganized and are often non-continuous. In Nigeria, the rapid development of universities and the rising students' population necessitates consistent training and retraining of lecturers to ensure that they remain effective in their teaching and academic responsibilities. Additionally, Ofor-Douglas (2019) opined that training involves arming your employees with more skills and knowledge on how best to perform their jobs or improve the skills they already have. However, Ingersoll (2017) maintained that well-prepared and continuously trained lecturers are more likely to stay in the profession, positively impacting students' outcomes over the long term. In a related view, continuous professional development (CPD) is vital for lecturers to keep up-to-date with new developments in their fields and to adopt innovative teaching methods that will apply in light of these new developments. It is worthy of note that training programs can positively impact teaching quality, leading to better learning outcomes for students (Xia et al, 2017). Furthermore, Falola et al. (2014) cited in Patrick (2021) pointed out that training fosters efficiency of the university and the effectiveness of every personnel. Additionally, it allows for continuous learning among lecturers, encouraging them to engage in self-improvement and professional development.

4. **Poor Contribution to Research by the University:** Another major challenge facing the capacity building of lecturers in Nigerian universities is the poor contribution to research by the universities. As earlier stated, the federal and state government holds the general responsibility of funding universities in Nigeria which also means that they are also responsible for the funding of research within the universities. The goal of consistent and continuous research and publication of research by lecturers in Nigerian universities is not forthcoming as the universities hardly provide the resources, both financial and material resources (internet facilities, textbooks and other research material) for the achievement of such goal. It is no wonder that Ofor-Douglas (2021) stated that funding is not forthcoming for research so lecturers are left little or no money to complete their research and this is preventing personal development. Furthermore, Ogunode et al (2020) pointed out that due to the general lack of commitment by the government at all levels, researchers are not given adequate financial support, researches carried out by professionals and associations are usually frustrated due to the lack of funds. Research productivity of a lecturer is vital for the advancement of societies and career growth of the lecturers in higher educational institutions (Ladipo et al, 2022). Aligning with this opinion, Ojelade, Aregbesola & Akinola (2017) emphasized that the society depends on educational research for sustainable development, to obtain reliable data and to fill the existing gap in research.

5. **Poor Motivation for Lecturers:** Another challenge facing capacity building of lecturers in Nigerian universities is that of poor motivation for lecturers. Motivation allows for positivity and productivity in the organization. Zipagan (2022) cited in Ofor-Douglas (2024e) mentioned that motivation is a driving force that inspires positive conduct or deeds at work and also improves the predisposition to remain committed. Lecturers in Nigerian universities are often discouraged from developing themselves simply because their development is dependent on financial resources in which they do not have. The poor salaries in which these lecturers are being paid does not encourage research and publications of articles. There is thus little or no motivation to engage in research and development activities which would aid in the advancement of the lecturers in their fields. Maxwell (2024) suggested that well-designed financial incentives can motivate lecturers to improve their teaching practices, leading to positive impacts on students learning.

CONCLUSION

The rate at which a university can reach optimum productivity is determined by the quality of lecturers which will in turn determine the quality of graduates released into the society. Capacity building is vital for lecturers in Nigerian universities to enhance their skills and knowledge in teaching and online facilitation, and to improve teaching and learning outcomes. In the 21st century university system, it is essential that lecturers continually seek to develop in terms of their teaching capacity so as to keep up with the trends of teaching in the university system. Thus, it is very important that universities in Nigeria pay close attention to building the capacity of their academic staff by aiding in their growth and development so as to ensure quality teaching within the university. In the same vein, the lecturers should utilize the opportunities provided by the university in developing their capacity as educators for the benefit of the students and the institution.

Suggestions

In order for capacity building of its lecturers to enhance productivity within universities in Nigeria, the following suggestions may be adopted:

1. The government, institutions, and stakeholders of Nigerian universities should ensure the provision of financial resource for capacity building of lecturers.
2. The universities should provide adequate materials for capacity building.
3. Priority should be giving to continuous professional development and adequate training and retraining of its lecturers through seminars, conferences and training workshops.
4. The university should provide adequate financial and research materials to the lecturers to improve research output and productivity to enable capacity building for these lecturers.
5. Providing financial incentives for researchers in the universities to carry out their research work without financial constraints.

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